

Dual Band Fractal Antenna for Wireless Sensor Network Application

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Abstract : A wireless sensor network (WSN) is a collection of sensor nodes organized into a cooperative network. These nodes communicate through a wireless antenna. Reduction in physical size and multiband operation is important requirement of WSN antenna. Fractal antenna is used for miniaturization and multiband operation. The self-similar or self-affine and space filling property of fractal geometry increases the effective electrical length of the antenna to reduce the size and make them frequency independent. This paper presents Dual band fractal antenna with Co-Planar Waveguide (CPW) Feed for WSN. The proposed antenna is designed on a FR4 substrate with the dimension of 27mmx 28.5mmx 1.6mm, resonates at 2.4GHz and 5.2GHz with a return loss less than -10dB. The design and simulation process is carried out using IE3D simulation software. The simulated and measured results are found in good agreement.

Keywords : CPW, Fractal, Iterations, Miniaturization, Space filling, Self Similar, WSN, WLAN.

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